

Availability Analysis of Filterless P2MP Horseshoe Networks under Load Shedding

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Abstract—Horseshoe filterless networks with point-to-multipoint (P2MP) transceivers are cost-effective but may lack resilience in regions with power outages. This paper addresses this gap by strategically placing amplifiers and couplers to enhance network resiliency. We evaluate the effectiveness of this approach through a network availability analysis.

Index Terms—Coherent point-to-multipoint, availability, survivable networks, amplifier placement, load shedding.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the realm of metro-aggregation networks, characterized by high bandwidth demands and strict reliability needs, strategically chosen physical layouts (e.g., horseshoe, ring) [1], [2] and transmission technologies play a crucial role in optimizing performance. The new Digital Subcarrier Coherent Multiplexing (DSCM)-enabled coherent point-to-multipoint (P2MP) transceivers offer a compelling alternative to traditional point-to-point (P2P) solutions [3]. This technology facilitates the aggregation of numerous low-volume traffic streams onto a single, high-capacity device at hub locations, leading to substantial enhancements in cost-effectiveness, power efficiency, and space utilization within the network [4].

Filterless optical networks (FONs) deviate from conventional Wavelength Division Multiplexing (WDM) by implementing passive splitters and combiners alongside a minimal set of fixed filters [5]. This replaces the reconfigurable add-drop multiplexers (ROADMs) employed in WDM with a simpler architecture. By integrating Digital Signal Constellation Modulation (DSCM) with this filterless design, the overall system requires significantly fewer active optical switches, filters, and power-hungry electronics for traffic aggregation [6], [7]. This reduction in complexity translates to simplified network management, substantial cost savings, and lower power consumption [2, 3]. However, it's important to acknowledge that FONs are most advantageous in scenarios where the required network capacity is considerably less than the available bandwidth within the C-band spectrum [8].

Service level agreements (SLAs) are contracts between a service provider and a customer that guarantee a certain quality of service (QoS). These agreements outline specific metrics,

like availability, to measure performance [9], [10]. If the service falls short of these metrics, the customer must be compensated. Fairness is a critical metric alongside efficiency. Resource allocation within the network should strive to be equitable for all connections or based on predefined SLAs. Focusing solely on minimizing overall resource consumption or cost can lead to unfairness, as some connections might be disproportionately impacted [11].

Due to inherent limitations, perfect uptime in optical networks is unattainable. Therefore, engineers leverage the concept of availability, a metric derived from historical failure and repair data (e.g., [12]), to quantify reliable system operation and the QoS. Network outages can stem from diverse causes such as fiber cuts, equipment malfunctions, human error, natural disasters, or power interruptions. A crucial strategy to enhance availability is redundancy, introducing multiple independent data paths [13]. However, achieving network survivability presents a steeper challenge in non-meshed filterless architectures due to limited fiber connectivity and restricted switching capabilities. To address this, additional equipment like wavelength blockers and color filters might be necessary [14]. Ultimately, network operators must find cost-effective solutions that respond to their specific circumstances, acknowledging the absence of a universal approach to maximize the availability of optical networks.

In designing fault-tolerant networks, most approaches rely on the unlikely occurrence of multiple failures [15]. However, this paradigm may be insufficient for scenarios with dense infrastructures (e.g., high fiber link counts) or increased failure rates due to external factors such as natural disasters and power outages.

Most of the protection solutions are based on the fact that two failures at the same time are extremely unlikely [15]. However, scenarios with more than two simultaneous failures should not always be neglected. In the event of single-link failures, services diverted to use other available links or use the already available redundant services exhibiting rapid recovery mechanisms with timescales on the order of milliseconds to seconds. However, repairs for such failures can be significantly longer process, requiring hours or even days [16]. This time window creates vulnerabilities to double-link/node

failures, where the second link/node fails before the first one is repaired. Network topologies, such as the horseshoe, may become susceptible to disruptions in connectivity for all leaf nodes. It is crucial to acknowledge that both isolated link failures and node failures can impact not only the failed element itself but also its connected links, as a failed node inherently impacts connections to both incoming and outgoing links. [17].

Reliability in electricity power directly impact the reliability of telecommunication networks. A critical challenge for network operators is maintaining performance when strategically induced power outages happening frequently. Load shedding, triggered by ageing electricity infrastructure, increased electrical energy demands, power grid failures, natural disasters [18], involves controlled blackouts in specific areas to prevent cascading failures across the entire grid. Depending on the shortage of electricity, the load shedding can be in different stages. Stage one requires the least power cut (e.g. 2-4 hours) while higher stages need more power cuts on top of the previous stages [19]. Traditional backup solutions, like generators and batteries, are deployed to mitigate these disruptions but incur significant costs compared to grid power [20], [21]. For instance, South African operators were forced to divert a substantial portion of their capital expenditure (12% of 2023 CapEx) towards backup power due to unreliable grid infrastructure. However, these investments introduce additional security concerns, as exposed sites with backup power become more vulnerable to theft and vandalism from surrounding communities experiencing outages, further escalating operational costs [22]. Therefore, designing networks with inherent redundancy and enhanced availability becomes vital to ensure reliable operation under these power-constrained circumstances. This paper proposes a filterless horseshoe network design employing P2MP transceivers, specifically optimized for its resilience against load shedding events.

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows. Section II discusses the details of our proposed architecture and ways in which it can be more reliable. In Section III, we propose an Integer Linear Programming (ILP) optimization framework with its input parameters, variables, and constraints specifically designed for the strategic or efficient deployment of optical amplifiers and couplers, while considering predefined practical design limitations. Finally, Section IV discusses the results obtained.

II. ARCHITECTURAL SOLUTION AND AVAILABILITY ANALYSIS METHODOLOGY

A horseshoe topology can inherently provide single-link and single-hub protection [1] due to redundant connections between leaf and hub nodes. The use of couplers instead of active switches significantly decreases the probability of node failure. In filterless networks, amplifiers play a more crucial role. They need to compensate for the combined impact of fiber attenuation and coupler losses.

A 5-leaf node filterless horseshoe network utilizing passive 2-by-2 coupler nodes is shown in Fig. 1(a). Amplifiers can be placed as booster pre-amplifiers at hubs and express/add-drop amplifiers at leaf nodes. Each leaf node is connected to both hub nodes via a main and protection path.

Power outages at leaf and hub nodes can significantly impact network functionality, particularly when affecting express amplifiers which amplify signals of multiple leaf nodes. Unlike fiber cuts that typically disrupt both signal directions, a downed express amplifier can effectively isolate segments within a single fiber path. The depicted scenario in Fig. 1(b) with a power outage at leaf 2 and a fiber cut between leaf nodes 4 and 5 exemplifies this, where leaf nodes 2, 3, and 4 lose connectivity to both hubs. This highlights the critical role of express amplifiers and the need for a robust design.

Our investigation focuses on the high risk of express amplifiers compared to add/drop amplifiers due to their role in amplifying signals for multiple channels. To enhance network resilience, strategies for minimizing or eliminating express amplifiers are explored, potentially transitioning express lines to a fully passive state. However, achieving full connectivity under such scenarios likely necessitates a more intensive use of add-drop amplifiers. Furthermore, the placement of express amplifiers significantly impacts network survivability. Network survivability exhibits a dependence on express amplifier placement. Horseshoe configurations with co-located express amplifiers, either within the same fiber or at a single leaf node but targeting different directions, demonstrate resilience (excluding directly affected nodes). Conversely, dispersing express amplifiers across separate leaf nodes and distinct fiber paths introduces a vulnerability for intermediate leaf nodes. This highlights the importance of strategic express amplifier placement to maximize network survivability. Consequently, we consider minimizing the number of amplification sites as the primary objective, not just total express amplifiers. Incorporating availability metrics directly into optimization frameworks can significantly enhance decision-making, but it also introduces non-linearity, which can complicate the optimization process.

Availability of an individual component can be expressed as mean time between failures (MTBF) and mean time to repair (MTTR) parameters.

$$A = 1 - \frac{MTTR}{MTBF} \quad (1)$$

Moreover, the unavailability U also can be calculated as $U = 1 - A$. We use availability data obtained from [23], [24] and presented in Table I in our analysis. For a communication link that is made of independent series of items, all items must be available at the same time to deliver the service. Therefore, the total availability can be written as follows:

$$A^T = \prod_{s=1}^S A^s \quad (2)$$

Fig. 1. Horseshoe filterless architecture and the vulnerability against (a) a power outage and a fiber cut and (b) two power outages at the same time.

TABLE I
INDIVIDUAL COMPONENTS UNAVAILABILITY [24], [23]

Individual Components Unavailability			
Component	MTBF khour	MTTR hour	$U = 1 - A$
Transceivers	196	2	$1.02 \cdot 10^{-5}$
Amplifiers	211	2	$9.48 \cdot 10^{-6}$
Couplers box	606	2	$3.3 \cdot 10^{-6}$
Fibers/km	364	2	$5.5 \cdot 10^{-6}$

A leaf node in a horseshoe network becomes unavailable only if both the main path and the protection path are unavailable at the same time.

$$U^l = U_{\text{main}}^l \times U_{\text{protection}}^l = (1 - A_{\text{main}}^l) \times (1 - A_{\text{protection}}^l) \quad (3)$$

The availability of both the main path and the protection path for each leaf node l can be represented mathematically as follows:

$$A_{\text{main}}^l = A_{\text{fiber}}^{|l-H1|} \times A_{\text{transceiver}}^2 \times A_{\text{coupler}}^l \times A_{\text{amplifier}}^{\delta_{b1} + \delta_{p1} + \delta_{a2} + \delta_{d1} + \sum_{a=1}^{l-1} \delta_{a12} + \delta_{a21}} \quad (4)$$

$$A_{\text{protection}}^l = A_{\text{fiber}}^{T-|l-H1|} \times A_{\text{transceiver}}^2 \times A_{\text{coupler}}^{|L|-l} \times A_{\text{amplifier}}^{\delta_{b2} + \delta_{p2} + \delta_{a1} + \delta_{d2} + \sum_{a=l+1}^{|L|+1} \delta_{a12} + \delta_{a21}} \quad (5)$$

Where T is total horseshoe length, and variable δ is one if there is a pre-amplifier (p), booster (b), add (a), drop (d) or express (12, 21) amplifiers. Note that the product of unavailability and time equals the expected amount of downtime during that period.

III. OPTIMIZATION FRAMEWORK

Three goals are of our interest in the proposed optimization framework for load shedding resilient filterless horseshoe networks:

- Number of amplification sites: this metric indicates the number of leaf nodes that contain at least one express amplifier. A higher number suggests a greater potential vulnerability to service disruptions during load shedding.
- Total number of amplifiers: this presents the total number of amplifiers including express, add/drop, and booster/pre-amplifiers. The cost of amplifiers is proportional to this parameter.
- Maximum subcarriers (SCs) power difference: this is one of the main DSCM-based P2MP transceiver parameters. With unequal SC power levels in upstream, low-power SCs only benefit from a portion of the available quantization levels, effectively reducing the dynamic range and effective number of bits (ENOB) for the analog-to-digital converter (ADC). This could degrade the Q-factor or the signal-to-noise ratio (OSNR) [25].

While minimizing all the goals mentioned above is crucial, they can often conflict. To address this, we significantly modify our original optimization framework in [1]. These changes enable us to consider all objectives simultaneously for both fiber directions, which are now interdependent. Moreover, the framework incorporates booster/pre-amplifiers for hub nodes, add/drop amplifiers for leaf nodes, and passive 2-by-2 couplers. We detail the key input parameters and decision variables in the following section.

Input Parameters

- L : List of leaf nodes.
- A : List of fiber links loss.
- G_g : EDFA gain range, 0 implies no amplifier.
- $M_d^{l,a}$: Binary link-path matrix ($|L| \times |A|$) from Hub1 to leaf nodes; 1 if path from Hub1 to leaf l contains link a .
- $M_u^{l,a}$: Binary link-path matrix ($|L| \times |A|$) from leaf nodes to Hub2; 1 if path from leaf l to Hub 2 contains link a .
- $N_d^{l,lx}$: Binary node-path matrix ($|L| \times |L|$) from Hub1 to leaf nodes; 1 if path from Hub1 to leaf l passes leaf lx .
- $N_u^{l,lx}$: Binary node-path matrix ($|L| \times |L|$) from leaf nodes to Hub2; 1 if path from leaf l to Hub2 passes leaf lx .
- P_l : Launch power per SC.
- P_n : Nonlinearity power threshold per SC.
- P_s : Sensitivity power level.
- P_x : SCs maximum power difference tolerance.
- H_s^p : Add/drop and express losses of coupler s .

Decision Variables

- $\Delta_{l,t}^s$: Binary variable for coupler selection; 1 if coupler s is selected for leaf l at direction t , 0 otherwise.
- $\gamma_{l,t}^p$: Loss of port p of coupler in leaf l in direction t .
- $\mu_{a,g}^{12}$: Binary variable; 1 if express amplifier on link a takes gain g for fiber direction Hub1 to Hub2.

- $\mu_{a,g}^{21}$: Binary variable; 1 if the amplifier at the link a takes the gain g for the fiber direction Hub2 to Hub1.
- $\mu_{l,g}^{d1}/\mu_{l,g}^{d2}$: Binary variables; 1 if drop amplifiers at leaf l takes gain g , otherwise 0.
- $\mu_{l,g}^{u1}/\mu_{l,g}^{u2}$: Binary variables; 1 if the add amplifiers at leaf l takes the gain g , otherwise 0.
- μ_g^{b1}/μ_g^{b2} : Binary variables; 1 if the booster amplifier at Hub1/Hub2 l takes the gain g , otherwise 0.
- μ_g^{p1}/μ_g^{p2} : Binary variable; 1 if the pre-amplifier at Hub1/Hub2 l takes the gain g , otherwise 0.
- ϕ_l^{12d} : Leaf l Rx power per SC coming from Hub1.
- ϕ_l^{12u} : Hub2 Rx power per SC coming from leaf l .
- ϕ_l^{21d} : Leaf l Rx power per SC coming from Hub2.
- ϕ_l^{21u} : Hub1 Rx power per SC coming from the leaf l .
- $\epsilon_{11}, \epsilon_{12}$: Lower and upper bounds of variables ϕ_l^{12u} .
- $\epsilon_{21}, \epsilon_{22}$: Lower and upper bounds of variables ϕ_l^{21u} .
- n_l : 1 if leaf l has at least one express amplifier, else 0.
- CF_l : criticality factor for leaf l .

Equation (6) expresses the objective function of the ILP model and consists of three terms.

$$z = w_1 N_s + N_t + w_2 [\epsilon_{12} - \epsilon_{11} + \epsilon_{22} - \epsilon_{21}] \quad (6)$$

where w_1 and w_2 are weight factors that determine the relative priority of each goal. $N_s = \sum_l CF_l \times n_l$ is the number of amplification sites while $N_t = \sum_a \sum_{g \neq 1} (\mu_{a,g}^{12} + \mu_{a,g}^{21}) G_g + \sum_l \sum_{g, g \neq 1} (\mu_{l,g}^{d1} + \mu_{l,g}^{d2} + \mu_{l,g}^{u1} + \mu_{l,g}^{u2} + \mu_g^{p1} + \mu_g^{p2} + \mu_g^{b1} + \mu_g^{b2}) G_g$ is the total number of amplifiers. The third term of the objective function is the total SCs power difference at the hubs' receivers, subject to the constraints described in the following.

$$\sum_g \mu_{XX}^{YY} = 1, \quad \forall a \in A \text{ or } l \in L \quad (7)$$

Constraints (7) choose an index for the gain of amplifiers in the network (XX and YY have to be replaced with appropriate indices for each set of amplifiers).

$$\sum_s \Delta_{l,t}^s = 1 \quad \forall l \in L, t \in \{12, 21\} \quad (8)$$

$$\gamma_{l,t}^p = \sum_s \Delta_{l,t}^s \times H_s^p \quad \forall l, t, p \in \{add/drop, exp\} \quad (9)$$

Constraints (8) are to select the couplers type at each leaf node. Also, constraints (9) assign the resulting loss to each port based on which coupler is selected.

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_l^{12d} &= -\gamma_{l,12}^{add/drop} - \sum_a A_a M_d^{l,a} - \sum_{lx} \gamma_{lx,12}^{exp} N_d^{l,lx} + P_l \\ &+ \sum_g (\mu_{l,g}^{d1} + \mu_{l,g}^{d2}) G_g + \sum_a \sum_g \mu_{a,g}^{12} G_g M_d^{l,a} \quad \forall l \in L \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_l^{12u} &= -\gamma_{l,12}^{add/drop} - \sum_a A_a M_u^{l,a} - \sum_{lx} \gamma_{lx,12}^{exp} N_u^{l,lx} + P_l \\ &+ \sum_g (\mu_{l,g}^{u1} + \mu_{l,g}^{u2}) G_g + \sum_a \sum_g \mu_{a,g}^{12} G_g M_u^{l,a} \quad \forall l \in L \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_l^{21d} &= -\gamma_{l,21}^{add/drop} - \sum_a A_a M_d^{l,a} - \sum_{lx} \gamma_{lx,21}^{exp} N_d^{l,lx} + P_l \\ &+ \sum_g (\mu_{l,g}^{d2} + \mu_{l,g}^{b2}) G_g + \sum_a \sum_g \mu_{a,g}^{21} G_g M_d^{l,a} \quad \forall l \in L \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_l^{21u} &= -\gamma_{l,21}^{add/drop} - \sum_a A_a M_d^{l,a} - \sum_{lx} \gamma_{lx,21}^{exp} N_d^{l,lx} + P_l \\ &+ \sum_g (\mu_{l,g}^{u2} + \mu_{l,g}^{p1}) G_g + \sum_a \sum_g \mu_{a,g}^{21} G_g M_d^{l,a} \quad \forall l \in L \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

Constraints (10) to (13) calculate the power received by the leaf nodes originating from Hub1, by Hub2, again by the leaf nodes but originating from Hub2, and by Hub1, respectively.

$$\phi_l^{XX} \geq P_s, \quad \forall l \in L, \quad (14)$$

The series of constraints listed in (14) ensure to meet the transceiver's sensitivity requirement.

$$\epsilon_{11} \geq \phi_l^{12u}, \quad \epsilon_{12} \leq \phi_l^{12u}, \quad \epsilon_{21} \geq \phi_l^{21u}, \quad \epsilon_{22} \leq \phi_l^{21u}, \quad (15)$$

$$\epsilon_{11} - \epsilon_{12} \leq P_x, \quad \epsilon_{21} - \epsilon_{22} \leq P_x, \quad (16)$$

The lower and upper bounds of the power levels received by transceivers in Hub1 and Hub2 from different leaf nodes are calculated by Eq. (15). Constraint (16) ensures that the difference between the highest and lowest SCs power levels (SCs power difference or SCs power imbalance) does not exceed the threshold defined for each transceiver located at the hub nodes. The rest of the constraints serve to maintain power levels per SC below a critical nonlinear power threshold across all designated critical points within the system.

$$\begin{aligned} & - \sum_a A_a M_d^{l,a} - \sum_{lx} \gamma_{lx,12}^{exp} N_d^{l,lx} - \gamma_{l,12}^{exp} + P_l + \\ & \sum_g \mu_g^{b1} G_g + \sum_a \sum_g \mu_{a,g}^{12} G_g M_d^{l,a} \leq P_n \quad \forall l \in L \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & - \sum_a A_a M_u^{l,a} - \sum_{lx} \gamma_{lx,21}^{exp} N_u^{l,lx} - \gamma_{l,21}^{exp} + P_l + \\ & \sum_g \mu_g^{b2} G_g + \sum_a \sum_g \mu_{a,g}^{21} G_g M_u^{l,a} \leq P_n \quad \forall l \in L \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

The constraints formulated in equations (17) and (18) act as safeguards to prevent the downstream signals from surpassing

a predetermined nonlinearity power threshold. This is achieved by guaranteeing that the amplifier output power, measured at the beginning of the main horseshoe links, does not exceed the established threshold level.

$$\begin{aligned}
P_l + \sum_g \mu_{l_n,g}^{u_1} G_g + \sum_{a,g} \mu_{a,g}^{12} G_g (M_u^{l_n,a} - M_u^{l_m,a}) \\
- \sum_a A_a (M_u^{l_n,a} - M_u^{l_m,a}) - \sum_{l_x} \gamma_{l_x,12}^{exp} (N_u^{l_n,l_x} - N_u^{l_m,l_x}) - \\
- \gamma_{l,12}^{add/drop} \leq P_n \quad \forall l_m \in L, l_n \in L, l_m \geq l_n
\end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
P_l + \sum_g \mu_{l_n,g}^{u_2} G_g + \sum_{a,g} \mu_{a,g}^{21} G_g (M_d^{l_n,a} - M_d^{l_m,a}) \\
- \sum_a A_a (M_d^{l_n,a} - M_d^{l_m,a}) - \sum_{l_x} \gamma_{l_x,21}^{exp} (N_d^{l_n,l_x} - N_d^{l_m,l_x}) - \\
- \gamma_{l,21}^{add/drop} \leq P_n \quad \forall l_m \in L, l_n \in L, l_m \geq l_n
\end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

Constraints (19) and (20) guarantee that the output power per upstream SC after each leaf node on the horseshoe remains within the limits established by the nonlinearity power threshold.

$$\sum_g \mu_g^{b_1} G_g + P_l \leq P_n \quad \sum_g \mu_g^{b_2} G_g + P_l \leq P_n \quad (21)$$

Constraints (21) ensure that the output power of booster amplifiers remain within the linear regime of fiber propagation.

$$M n_l \geq \sum_{l=1}^{|L|} \sum_g \mu_{l,g}^{12} G_g + \sum_{l=2}^{|L|+1} \sum_g \mu_{l,g}^{21} G_g \quad \forall l \in L \quad (22)$$

Constraint (22) calculates the number of express amplification sites n_l using an enough large number M . If right-hand side is 1 or more, n_l must be 1 to satisfy the constraint.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This work presents an optimization framework for horseshoe network topologies, incorporating relevant network parameters and constraints. The transceivers employ a dual-polarization 16-QAM modulation format, requiring a minimum received power per SC of -22 dBm. The launch power is set to the maximum permissible value of -12 dBm/SC for all transceivers. To mitigate nonlinear interference, a power constraint of -8 dBm/SC is imposed as the upper bound for fiber launch power. The network utilizes single-mode fibers with an attenuation coefficient of 0.25 dB/km. An excess loss of 0.7 dB is factored in on top of the splitting loss for the employed couplers. The power differential of SCs at the hub receivers is restricted not to exceed a threshold denoted by P_x (set to 8 dB in this study). Amplifier gains are constrained within a range of 10 dB to 20 dB, with 1 dB increments. The optimization framework, detailed in Section III, was

implemented using Julia programming (particularly the JuMP package). All problem instances were solved using the CPLEX solver.

Figure 2 analyzes unavailability for three coupler scenarios averaged across 25 horseshoe networks (modeled using horseshoes in [2]). The "50:50" scenario restricts coupler choices, while "70:30 & 90:10" allows more flexibility. Finally, the "All" scenario offers the optimization tool the widest range of couplers (10% to 90% ratios in 10% increments). As can be seen, the unavailability is generally higher for central leaf nodes (because the failure of main and protection paths simultaneously is more likely) for these leaf nodes. Additionally, the "50:50" scenario with its increased reliance on amplifiers introduces more potential failure points, raising unavailability.

Fig. 2. Average unavailability of the horseshoe network when considering different coupler ratios.

In the event of a link failure, the horseshoe network converts into two separate trees with unequal sizes depending on the location of the break. Figure 3 depicts the average network unavailability caused by a random link failure. As the figure illustrates, unavailability increases by more than three orders of magnitude. This demonstrates the horseshoe network's significant vulnerability after a single link failure.

Fig. 3. Average unavailability of the horseshoe when a link is failed.

Regarding load shedding, another layer of unreliability is added on top of natural network unreliability. If we assume power availability as P_{av} , the unavailability of the leaf nodes under loadshedding can be presented as $U_{loadshedding}^l = 1 -$

$P_{ave}*(1-U^l) = P_{unav} + P_{av}U^l$ where U^l is the unavailability caused by unavailability of power in the rest of the network and $P_{unav} = 1 - P_{av}$. In other words, power unavailability affects the leaf node availability in two ways; 1) directly (first term in above expression) and 2) by interrupting links in other locations (indirect-second term). Consequently, the lower limit of unavailability is limited by power unavailability.

Fig.4 shows the $U_{loadshedding}^l$ (based on the above definition and in terms of percentage - 1% is equal to 5250 min /year) when power availability is independent in different leaf nodes and equal to 98%, 95%, and 90% for "50:50" scenario. We assume hub nodes always have back-up power. As it can be seen, overall, amplification site minimization provides less unavailability decreasing the second term of the unavailability by up to 45% compared to amplifier minimization. Note that a higher power unavailability introduces more indirect effects as well. Leaf nodes closer to hub nodes tend to experience less downtime because they are less likely to be impacted by neighboring leaf nodes power outages and failures. Considering unbalanced couplers diminishes even further as a greater number of express amplifiers can be moved to add/drop.

Fig. 4. Average unavailability of the horseshoe network under loadshedding.

V. CONCLUSIONS

We proposed a load shedding-resilient filterless horseshoe network utilizing DSCM-based P2MP transceivers. The proposed multi-objective ILP model can prioritize minimizing the number of express amplification sites (representing vulnerability). The results of availability analysis showed that the horseshoe network is very resistant to single failures (like a single cable breaking) but can still be affected by external events like large-scale power outages.

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